

VOLUMETRIC QUANTIFICATION OF BRIDGING AND WRINKLING DEFECTS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATESCooper Williams¹, Dr. Cecily Ryan¹, Dr. Jared Nelson², Dr. Douglas Cairns^{1*}, and Christopher Ridgard^{1*}

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Keywords: Carbon Fiber Composites, Laminates, Prepreg, Defects, Discontinuous Fibers

ABSTRACT

Stretch broken carbon fiber (SBCF) offers enhanced formability over traditional continuous carbon fiber (CCF) while retaining comparable mechanical properties. Leveraging this advantage, SBCF has the potential to reduce the formation and severity of common laminate defects such as wrinkling and bridging. This study introduces and applies volumetric methods for quantifying these defects with improved accuracy and resolution. Two SBCF and two CCF quasi-isotropic laminates were manufactured in a curved c-channel geometry and analyzed using 3D scan data and updated image processing methods. Results showed that the Montana State University (MSU)-developed SBCF laminates outperformed their CCF counterparts in terms of bridging behavior, exhibiting significantly lower average bridging volume and variability across both inner and outer radii of the channel. In contrast, both material systems yielded comparable wrinkling based on the defect scoring method discussed herein. However, there were differences observed in the wrinkling behavior between CCF and SBCF laminates with similar scores. While CCF laminates exhibited a higher frequency of and more broadly located wrinkles, SBCF laminates showed fewer wrinkles of larger average magnitude, particularly in non-critical regions. These findings reinforce SBCF as a promising material system for complex forming applications and highlight the need for further optimization to reduce wrinkling, particularly when occurring in critical regions.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber (CF) composites are widely employed in performance-driven industries such as aerospace, automotive, and sporting goods due to their high tensile strength-to-weight ratio and design flexibility. These properties make them particularly desirable for structural applications where being lightweight and stiffness are critical material considerations. Fiber-reinforced composites are generally categorized into two groups: continuous fiber and discontinuous fiber systems. Continuous carbon fibers (CCF) are commonly used in pre-impregnated (prepreg) laminates for specific, efficiency focused applications. However, the limited maximum strain and inability for fibers within a CF tow to stretch and displace with respect to other fibers, can present significant challenges during the layup of complex geometries. Defects such as bridging and wrinkling are likely to occur in these geometries, limiting application due to manufacturability and performance [5, 6, 8].

Aligned, discontinuous fiber systems, such as stretch broken carbon fiber (SBCF), have been proposed as a more formable alternative for complex laminate geometries. SBCF laminates offer an improved ability to conform to complex geometries, making it a promising candidate for next-generation composite structures. Researchers at Montana State University (MSU) [1-3,7,10] have made significant

progress in developing an SBCF prepreg system and are actively evaluating its forming behavior in geometrically challenging applications, using CCF laminates as a performance benchmark.

This study focuses on two critical laminate defects: wrinkling and bridging [4]. By quantifying these defects across both SBCF and CCF material systems within a specified complex geometry, the curved c-channel, this work aims to assess the formability of MSU SBCF material, identify successful forming strategies, and evaluate metrics related to the material's potential for use in industrial composite component manufacturing.

METHODOLOGY

Laminate Manufacturing

Six laminates were manufactured for this study; three of which were continuous unidirectional Syensqo Hexcel 12k IM7 CYCOM® 977-3 carbon fiber prepreg [12]. The remaining three laminates were made with unidirectional MSU SBCF carbon fiber prepreg. This SBCF prepreg was made in conjunction with the University of Southern Mississippi using MSU stretch broken Hexcel 12k IM7 fibers and CYCOM® 977-3 resin system [11-12]. All laminates, CCF and SBCF, were eight-ply, quasi-isotropic, $[45/0/-45/90]_S$ to maintain consistency with laminates evaluated in previous MSU SBCF program studies [1]. The laminates for this study were formed into a curved c-channel geometry, Figure 1, following the layup method used in previous studies, also with the purpose of maintaining consistency [1]. This method is described briefly below.

Figure 1: Curved c-channel aluminum mold used for previous program laminates in [1].

During manufacturing, 9-inch square plies were laid up in pairs and formed to the mold starting in the corner where the radii are centered. The plies were then worked across the surface of the mold, down the inner radius face, across the bottom of the channel, up the outer radius face, and onto the larger flat area towards the diagonal corner of the start. The newest curved c-channel mold, the mold for these studies, has been expanded by 1.5 inches in length and width from the mold used in previous studies to accommodate grit strips to secure material edges during forming. During the layup, plies were formed by hand using 200°F [93.3°C] via heat gun to increase the pliability of the two-ply sub-laminate. Once initially placed, the same heat and force was then applied to the pair of plies to enhance forming and smooth out wrinkles that may have formed. A silicon intensifier was placed onto the laminate after the layup was completed. Figure 2 shows the completed layup with the grit strips and intensifier. The laminate was then vacuum bagged and debulked for 20 minutes before curing in an autoclave. The autoclave recipe for all laminates in this study follows the current recipe for curing MSU SBCF parts: the autoclave is initially ramped to 200°F [93.3°C] for 30 minutes before a 4-hour dwell at 250°F [121°C]. This cure cycle has been developed from forming evaluations of SBCF parts during autoclave

curing in previous program studies [1-2]. During the autoclave cure, the grit strips mitigate slipping on the ply-mold interface. After curing completed, the laminate was demolded and trimmed to a 6 inch by 6-inch square. Sharp edges were then sanded away for handling.

Figure 2: Complete curved c-channel layup ready for bag.

Wrinkling Analysis

After the laminate was cured, trimmed, and sanded, it was scanned in 3-dimensions using a Keyence VL-800 Series 3D scanner. The scan produces a point cloud with about 300,000 points and an STL mesh of the scanned laminate. Once scanning was completed, the rectangular footprint (boxed in Figure 3) of each observable wrinkle was directly measured and recorded with dial calipers for later use. The critical area—the main channel and circled in Figure 3 – is where wrinkles would be most concerning. The non critical area outside of the circle is of lesser, but substantial, concern.

Figure 3: Curved c-channel laminate after complete wrinkle measurement.

3D scans of laminates were analyzed using CloudCompare. A reference mesh of the as-designed, ideal laminate is imported into the software as is the STL mesh of the scanned laminate. These two meshes are then scaled and aligned. Using CloudCompare's cloud to mesh (C2M) comparison tool, the distance between the reference mesh and various groups of points in the scanned mesh—usually around 50,000 groups—can be calculated. This analysis yields a displacement mapping of the scanned laminate onto the original, highlighting where the greatest distances between the two are. An example of results from this process is shown in Figure 6 below. Wrinkles are easily visible; they can be easily identified, isolated, and labeled for individual analysis. Using a Gaussian distribution tool in CloudCompare, the Gaussian mean distance of each wrinkle from the reference was determined and recorded. This mean was then multiplied across the rectangular footprint of each wrinkle to determine a volumetric approximation of the wrinkle size.

With the 3D scans, all laminate wrinkles were analyzed to create a more complete understanding of SBCF wrinkling during forming. Therefore, wrinkles can be analyzed both in the critical area, circled in Figure 3, as done in prior studies and in the submitted conference abstract, as well as more broadly across the parts. This full-part analysis allows for a more complete understanding and quantification of wrinkling frequency, magnitude, and location during forming. Additionally, it is important to note that the techniques of the MSU SBCF Parts and Structures Manufacturing group have progressed to where wrinkling rarely occurs on critical surfaces. Wrinkles on the critical area and noncritical areas of each laminate are denoted separately for further analysis.

Bridging Analysis

After the wrinkling analysis was complete, each laminate is cut every 15° from 0° to 90°, as depicted in Figure 4. Section faces were sanded for imaging at the inner and outer radii to obtain the cross-sectional area for bridging measurements and calculations.

Figure 4: Sectioned curved c-channel showing the slices made for the bridging analysis.

Figure 5 depicts the cross section of both the inner and outer radii of Figure 1, as both have the same cross-sectional geometry and a fillet of 0.125 in radius. Using ImageJ, measurements of the distance, L_x and L_y , between the laminate-mold contact point and the perpendicular mold surface were collected from images. The lengths measured were used to calculate the cross-sectional area of the bridging space. L_x and L_y were first used to find the area of the red rectangle, Figure 5, and then used to find the area of the ellipse formed by the laminate. The area of the ellipse was then subtracted from the areas of the rectangle and fillet. The result of this calculation is the area of space generated from bridging, measured in square inches. This area was then extended over a fraction of the length of the curve perpendicular to the cross section in such that each area possesses equal length relative to all other calculated areas for a given radius. For example, if there are twelve faces, that of Figure 4, created along a radius of curvature with an arc length—such as the orange arc of Figure 3—of six inches, the cross-sectional area of each face is extrapolated over 0.5 inches of the total six inches. This analysis assumes that the surface created when the laminate was cut is an adequate representation of bridging for the surrounding area of the radius through this extreme region of the geometry.

Figure 5: Curved c-channel cross-section and location of measurements to calculate bridging volume.

Table 1: Variables for Calculating Bridging Volume

Variable	Definition
r_f	Fillet radius, 0.25 in.
i	Cross-sectional face being measured, ND*.
L_{yi}	Vertical length from point of tangency to perpendicular mold surface at i , in.
L_{xi}	Horizontal length from point of tangency to perpendicular mold surface at i , in.
A_e	Cross-sectional Ellipse area, in. ²
A_R	Cross-sectional Rectangle area, in. ²
A_B	Cross-sectional Bridging area, in. ²
l_{ARC}	Length of curvature of concern, in.
N	Total number of cross-sectional faces created, ND*.
V_B	Volume of Bridging, in. ³

*ND: Non-dimensional

Equation 1, below, describes the summation of small sections of volumes for each face created when cutting the laminate at the specified angles shown in Figure 4. These volumes are generated by multiplying the cross-sectional area of bridging (blue boxed term in Equation 1) by a fraction of the area's guide curve (orange boxed term in Equation 1). The terms in the blue box of Equation 1 represent the subtraction of the ellipse's area from the red rectangle's area plus the small cross-sectional area of the fillet, Figure 5. The term boxed in orange, below, describes a fraction of the cross-sectional area's guide curve. The outer and inner radii are the guide curves of this geometry. The length of the arc, l_{ARC} , is simply the total length of the outer or inner radius, depending on the radius of curvature. Multiplying the blue and orange terms of Equation 1 generates the volumetric measurement of bridging in cubic inches.

$$\sum_{n=0}^N \left[\left((L_y \cdot L_x) - \frac{\pi \cdot L_{yi} \cdot L_{xi}}{4} + (r_f^2 - \frac{\pi \cdot r_f^2}{4}) \right) \cdot \left[\frac{l_{ARC}}{N} \right] \right] = V_B \quad (1)$$

Cutting a curved c-channel laminate, as previously discussed, creates twelve cross-sectional faces: one at 0°, another at 90°, and two at every remaining cut site. Thus, in Equations 1 and 2, the inner and outer radii lengths were sectioned into twelfths for the purpose of these equations. These equations were used to extrapolate the cross-sectional area along a portion of the extreme radius such that each volume was equal in the length it spans. The summation of these twelve volume approximations formed a 3D model of the total volume created by bridging for the geometry under inspection (variables are listed in Table 1).

Equation 2 is a simplified version of Equation 1. It uses the same variables but establishes a constant that represents subtracting one-quarter of an ellipse from a rectangle whose sides are equal to the major and minor axes of the ellipse. This constant, in the purple box of Equation 2, assumes that the laminate maintains a smooth, elliptical cross-sectional profile. Equation 2 also introduces the constant

cross-sectional area of the fillet in square inches, the green box, since the fillet is of a known, constant value. Equation 2 was used to determine the total bridging volume estimate.

$$\sum_{n=0}^N \left[\left((L_{yi} L_{xi}) * \left(1 - \frac{\pi}{4} \right) + 0.00353 \right) * \frac{l_{ARC}}{N} \right] = V_B \quad (2)$$

It is important to note that equations 1 and 2 are specific to calculations for this geometry and represent the application of this quantification process to the curved c-channel. The principles of this method can be applied to any concave laminate of interest where bridging may occur. In future work, similar calculations will be extended for use in other geometries. The key feature of this approach is that a model of the space created by bridging can be established using cross-sectional measurements to define bridging and extrapolated over an appropriate perpendicular arc length. This calculation is repeated at each face created from cutting, and the resulting volumes are summed to form a comprehensive volumetric bridging model of the laminate.

NOMENCLATURE

Table 2: Sample Laminate Labelling

Sample Number	Continuous Fiber (CF)	Stretch Broken Carbon Fiber (SBCF)
1	CF01	SBCF01
2	CF02	SBCF02
3	CF03	SBCF03

RESULTS

Due to a layup error, laminate SBCF01 was found to be asymmetric and was therefore excluded from further wrinkling analysis in this study. The nonconformity rendered its scans unusable for 3D wrinkle characterization. To maintain balanced sample sizes between SBCF and CCF groups, wrinkling data for CF02 are also withheld.

Wrinkling Analysis Results

The greatest number of wrinkles was observed in CF01, which exhibited twelve distinct wrinkles. All the other laminates presented eight wrinkles each. Wrinkles were primarily located in non-critical regions of the laminate geometry, with the exception of a single critical-region wrinkle observed in CF03. SBCF01 and SBCF03 exhibited larger average wrinkle volumes than either of the continuous fiber laminates: 0.00589 in³ and 0.00711 in³, respectively. In comparison, CF01 and CF03 had average wrinkle volumes of 0.00221 in³ and 0.00309 in³, respectively. The stretch-broken fiber laminates also demonstrated greater variability in wrinkle size, with standard deviations of 0.00745 in³ in SBCF02 and 0.006013 in³ in SBCF03.

Figure 6: Complete CloudCompare C2M analysis of SBCF03. Both scales display inches, which may marginally deviate through a scaling factor.

Figure 6 depicts a completed CloudCompare C2M (Cloud-to-Mesh) analysis used to quantify wrinkle geometry. This analysis was similarly performed for CF01, CF02, and SBCF02, isolated wrinkles are displayed in Table 3. In Figure 6, wrinkle locations correspond to areas of maximum deviation from the nominal surface geometry. Areas near 0 in of deformation are shown in blue while areas of high deformation approaching 0.01188 in are shown in red. Green, yellow, and orange areas depict increasing distances from the designed part, respectively. Wrinkles were shown highlighted and easily observed as green and yellow areas of Figure 6. All eight wrinkles in SBCF03 were located on the large, non-critical zone of the part, a trend observed across most laminates in the study. Notably, SBCF02 exhibited both the largest and smallest wrinkles by volume, measured at 0.228 in³ and 0.0005 in³, respectively. This range underscores the variability in wrinkle severity found in stretch broken laminates compared to their continuous fiber counterparts.

Table 3 below shows the isolated wrinkles of each laminate after the initial alignment is completed. These wrinkles are located mainly on the top flange as previously discussed and can dramatically vary in size. Many of the wrinkles are either aligned with the fiber axis of the +45° plies or the corner where layup begins. Color scales for these wrinkles also widely vary as they are typically one of the largest deformations in a laminate and can have varying prominence, meaning that the height of the wrinkle itself varies with respect to the height of the surface it propagates on.

Table 3: Images of isolated wrinkles of all analyzed laminates

*Laminate scales are in inches and marginally deviate from designed laminate part through a scaling factor.

Bridging Analysis Results

CF02 exhibited the highest average bridging volume along both the inner and outer radii, measured at 0.01182 in^3 and 0.00916 in^3 , respectively. The variance of CF02 was also larger than all other laminates: $5.81130\text{E-}05 \text{ in}^6$ at the inner radius and $2.15772\text{E-}05 \text{ in}^6$ at the outer radius. SBCF02 showed the lowest average bridging volumes across both regions, 0.00230 in^3 (inner) and 0.00381 in^3 (outer), and also exhibited the lowest variance: $3.75586\text{E-}07 \text{ in}^6$ (inner) and $3.99120\text{E-}07 \text{ in}^6$ (outer). At both radii, SBCF01 displayed average bridging comparable to CF01—the best CF laminate in terms of bridging—but performed the worst among SBCF laminates with average bridging at the inner radius of 0.00643 in^3 and 0.00584 in^3 at the outer radius. SBCF02 and SBCF03 showed low bridging with maximum average bridging at either radius of 0.00381 in^3 and 0.00412 in^3 , respectively.

Figure 7: Average inner radius bridging volume of all laminates.

Figure 8: Average outer radius bridging volume of all laminates.

The x-axes of Figure 9 and Figure 10 correspond with the cuts shown in Figure 4, not ply fiber angle. All laminates exhibit a local peak in bridging volume near the 45° face cuts, Figure 4, with this effect more pronounced in the continuous fiber laminates. In addition to having the highest average bridging volumes, CF02 also shows both the highest and lowest bridging occurrences at the outer radius, indicating a broader spread in localized bridging severity. Similar to the average bridging behavior, the forming of SBCF01 is comparable to that of the CF laminates but is much greater than other SBCF laminates, especially at extreme geometry. In contrast, SBCF02 and SBCF03 laminates demonstrate the most consistent bridging behavior across both radii while maintaining low bridging volumes, as shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. At the inner radius, continuous fiber laminates demonstrate poor forming to the concave radius as the curve of the channel becomes more aggressive; but bridging decreases at the 0° and 90° cuts. Conversely, SBCF laminates exhibit low amounts of bridging across the curve with fluctuations throughout.

Figure 9: Inner radius bridging volume mapping.

Similar to their behavior at the inner radius, continuous fiber laminates at the outer radius of the curved c-channel exhibited greater bridging towards the extreme portions of the curve, with better conformity before and after this section of geometry. The stretch broken laminates outer bridging performance was also comparable to their bridging performance at the inner radius, again with SBCF01 as an outlier. SBCF03 had a lower range of bridging volume throughout the laminate with stronger local fluctuations at the most aggressive portions of the geometry. Notably, SBCF02 demonstrated outstanding bridging performance, maintaining a low, nearly constant bridging volume around the curvature.

Figure 10: Outer radius bridging volume mapping.

DISCUSSION

Wrinkling Analysis Discussion

The higher variability of wrinkle magnitude and comparable wrinkle propagation in SBCF laminates compared to CCF laminates indicates that SBCF may also be more sensitive to local

disturbances during layup and curing given that the current MSU SBCF laminate manufacturing practices are under continual development, and current practices may still allow small process inconsistencies to manifest as wrinkles and other defects. The consistent wrinkle locations of this study loosely align with wrinkling from previous studies, despite more refined manufacturing processes [1]. The larger non-critical flange regions are more susceptible to wrinkling, likely due to the layup technique and residual forming forces induced during layup and curing. Wrinkling at this flange emphasizes the consideration placed on tooling design and layup practices, such as tension control when working with this material.

The present wrinkling analysis between CCF and SBCF materials does not clearly indicate which material is better suited to avoiding laminate wrinkling. The consistent presence of wrinkles in both materials highlights residual challenges in achieving defect-free forming. The wrinkling behavior of CCF laminates may be within the expected bounds for unidirectional laminates of this geometry, but the ceiling for formability for SBCF laminates is much higher than demonstrated in this study. As optimal SBCF laminate manufacturing practices such as tooling design, vacuum bag configuration, layup technique, and strategic intensifier use continue to be identified and refined, it is probable that SBCF part conformity will improve, especially for this geometry.

Bridging Analysis Discussion

As the laminates form to the mold geometry during forming, the 0° and 90° plies are primarily subjected to transverse in-plane tension, particularly near the extreme regions of curvature where stress concentrations are highest. The ±45° plies behave differently under deformation: the +45° plies experience in-plane longitudinal tension, while the -45° plies are subjected to in-plane orthogonal tension. At both the inner and outer radii, CCF tend to bridge as they span the concave geometry, constrained by their high tensile stiffness and limited ability to stretch. In contrast, the SBCF laminates demonstrate improved conformity in these regions. This increased geometric conformity is attributed to the shorter, discontinuous but aligned fiber segments that characterize SBCF materials, which allow for higher effective stretch ratio without theoretically significantly sacrificing composite properties. The reduced fiber lengths in SBCF laminates not only improve formability but also significantly lower the likelihood of bridging in concave regions.

While Figure 9 and Figure 10 may initially suggest that bridging is more severe at the outer radius than the inner, this comparison is misleading due to differences in arc length between the two regions. The outer radius spans a longer arc (7.854 in) than the inner radius (4.712 in), which inherently increases the calculated bridging volume at the outer radius (Equation 2), regardless of actual bridging severity. This difference allows for the direct comparison of a specific radii between laminates but not between the inner and outer radii of a given laminate.

In addition, the use of a silicon intensifier during autoclave processing has become a critical feature of MSU's SBCF laminate manufacturing approach. In this study, it played an important role in enhancing forming quality by reducing bridging and alleviating layup "touch" time. Bridging has been a challenge for previous SBCF programs due to fiber length [9]; however, the MSU SBCF laminates significantly outperformed the continuous fiber laminates in terms of bridging behavior in the c-channel geometry of this study. The results of this study have direct implications for manufacturing curved composite components where conformability, labor efficiency, and defect tolerance are critical, such as an aerospace stiffener design or automotive reinforcements.

CONCLUSION

Forming an eight-ply quasi-isotropic prepreg laminate into a curved c-channel geometry provided valuable insights into the layup, forming, and curing procedures and preliminary defect behavior of MSU's SBCF material system in complex structures. Using CCF laminates as a control enabled direct benchmarking of bridging and wrinkling performance under identical geometric and process constraints.

The CCF laminates exhibited significant bridging, particularly in regions of high curvature, along with wrinkling defects in both critical and non-critical areas. In contrast, two of the SBCF laminates demonstrated improved bridging performance, with reduced defect volume and variability across the inner and outer radii. However, SBCF laminates also showed comparable, yet slightly higher average wrinkle volumes compared to their continuous fiber counterparts, despite similar wrinkle counts. None of the wrinkles in SBCF laminates were in critical regions. While no definitive material preference can be established from this study alone, the findings suggest that with further refinement in processing techniques, SBCF materials have strong potential for use in complex-forming applications, especially where bridging is a limiting defect.

Additionally, this work provides valuable insights regarding the effectiveness of these new quantification methods. The bridging system worked as intended without any unforeseen challenges. The wrinkling system, however, was particularly challenged in the analysis of laminates with high macroscopic deviation from the designed laminate, such as SBCF01. This challenge will be overcome as the wrinkling analysis process is refined, and knowledge gaps will be filled accordingly.

FUTURE WORK

Subsequent studies will focus on expanding the defect characterization framework by employing next-generation metrics similar to those used for bridging and wrinkling in this study. Particular attention will be given to understanding the behavior of SBCF materials in concave radii, where corner thickening is observed; furthermore, the mechanisms and mitigation strategies for this phenomenon are outside the scope of the present study, they will be addressed in future work. Understanding, quantifying, and potentially mitigating this effect will be essential for enabling the broader adoption of SBCF laminates in geometrically complex structural components, including the curved c-channel. Another future focus will be to expand the types of complex geometries that are evaluated for forming complex structures using this rigorous defect quantification scheme. As the production of MSU SBCF output increases in volume and quality, as outlined in [3], a growing catalog of laminate quality evaluations will guide the optimization of MSU SBCF applications and manufacturing techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Montana State University would like to acknowledge the contribution of the US Army which has funded much of the recent development work. Agency: US Department of the Army; Award Number: W911W6-18-C-0050. The views and conclusions contained in this document are those of the authors and should not be interpreted as necessarily representing the official policies, either expressed or implied, of the Government.

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